

SPALL DAMAGE OF ALUMINA/ALUMINUM COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The mechanism of the initial spall damage of an aluminum matrix composite reinforced with short alumina fibers is investigated with the plate impact tests. The target plates, composed of 99.9% pure aluminum and alumina fibers of $3\mu\text{m}$ in diameter and $200\mu\text{m}$ in length, were impacted with the flyer plates of steel or the composite at a speed of $100\text{--}250\text{m/s}$, which would caused the impact stress of $0.8\text{--}2.6\text{GPa}$. It has been shown that the threshold stress for spallation would be 2GPa for the composite while 0.8GPa for aluminum matrix. The SEM micrographs show the spallation occurs along the fibers, particularly on only one side of the fibers.

Key words: Spall, Composite, MMC, Damage, Alumina/aluminum composite.

1. INTRODUCTION

Spall damage, which is caused by high tensile stress wave in uniaxial strain condition, has been extensively

studied for the monolithic metals(1-3). The mechanisms of the nucleation and growth of the spall damage has well understood for metals. For spallation of metal matrix composites, however, only a few investigations have been published (4,5). Those are concerned with the MMC reinforced with long fibers.

Recently metal matrix composites reinforced with short fibers have been developed for aerospace and civilian use, because of relatively high specific-stiffness and strength as well as availability of the usual manufacturing processes of metals. The static strength and fatigue of MMC reinforces with short fibers have been investigated(6), however, no report has been published for the spall strength of the material.

In this paper, the mechanisms of the initial spall damage of an aluminum matrix composite reinforced with short alumina fibers are investigated with the plate impact test. The difference between the composite and aluminum matrix itself is discussed for the nucleation and growth of microvoids or microcracks based on observation of the damage with scanning electron microscope and acoustic microscope.

2. MATERIAL AND EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

2.1 Test specimen

The composite plates tested were manufactured by the squeeze casting, in which pure molten aluminum(1N90) permeated the alumina preforms composed of almost uniaxially aligned fibers(Figure 1) of which properties are shown in Table 1 and were solidified under high hydrostatic pressure(7). The fiber volume fraction was about 20% and the fibers were parallel to the plate surfaces. It should be noted that the fibers are not perfectly straight nor aligned perfectly uniaxially.

For the sake of comparison, aluminum matrix itself and commercially pure aluminum(1050) plates were also tested. The target plates (60mm in diameter and 8mm in thickness) were machined from these plates. Aluminum and mild steel plates(thickness 4mm and 60mm in diameter) were used for the flyers.

Table 1. Properties of alumina fiber.

Composites	Al ₂ O ₃ : 95 %, SiO ₂ : 5 %
Average diameter	3 μ m
Average length	200 μ m
Density	3.3 g/cm ³
Tensile strength	2 GPa
Young's modulus	300 GPa

Figure 1. Micrograph of composite. Parallel to fibers.

2.2 Experimental apparatus

The gas gun of bore 100mm in which highly pressurized nitrogen gas was the propellant was used to accelerate the flyer. At the end of the barrel, the cylinder shown in Figure 2 was attached, with which the velocity of the flyer was measured and the target sabot was kept to the right position. The impact velocity of the flyer was measured with optical fiber switches located apart 100 mm(error: 200±7m/s). The target and flyer plates were adhered to the sabots shown in Figure 3 within perpendicularity tolerance 0.7 mrad with respect to the axis of the sabot.

Figure 2. Apparatus for velocity measurement.

Figure 3. Flyer and target assembly.

2.3 Experimental procedure

Before and after the plate impact tests, the ultrasonic energy attenuation of the target plates was measured with a normal incidence wave transducer (5MHz). After the impact test, the probable locations of spallation, estimated by the ultrasonic test, of the target plates were sectioned and observed with SEM. In addition, those locations were examined with an acoustic microscope to visualize the distribution of voids and cracks in the target.

3. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Threshold stress for spallation

The impact velocity, impact stress estimated by Equation (1), and appearance of the spall damage are summarized in Table 2.

$$\sigma = \frac{\rho_f C_f \rho_t C_t}{\rho_f C_f + \rho_t C_t} V \quad (1)$$

where ρ , C and V denote the density, bulk wave velocity in the target and the velocity of the flyer. The suffixes f and t denote the flyer and target. The initiation of the spall damage was judged from the appearance of aligned microvoids or microcracks of a few micron meter.

The threshold stress of spallation is about 0.8GPa for the aluminum matrix and 1050 aluminum, but it is about 2GPa for the composite. The short fibers are aligned parallel to the impacted surface, however, they work effectively to strengthen the threshold stress of spallation.

Table 2. Summary of impact tests.

	1050	1N90	Alumina/Al composite				
Specimen No.	11	4P	11C	16C	3C2	18C	19C
Impact Velocity(m/s)	90	120	160	180	190	220	240
Impact Stress (GPa)	0.6	0.8	1.2	2.0	2.1	2.4	2.6
Spall Damage	×	○	×	○	○	○	○

3.2 Mechanisms of nucleation and growth of microvoids or cracks

The microcracks in the composite and microvoids in 1050 aluminum are shown in Figures 4–6. In the composite microcracks or coalesced microvoids appear only along one side of the fibers, namely on the side impacted. It should be noted that only a few fibers are well identified in Figures 4 and 5, however, there are so many fibers as shown in Figure 7. In contrast to the composite, aligned ductile voids are observed in 1050 aluminum. At higher stress (Figure 7), fibers themselves had broken in the transverse as well as longitudinal directions. The cracking in fibers is also observed in Figure 7, in which the aluminum matrix was slightly etched by hydrofluoric acid.

One probable explanation for this type of cracking is as follows: The alumina fibers have the higher acoustic impedance than the aluminum matrix, therefore, the tensile wave is partially reflected on the fiber–matrix interfaces. The higher tensile stress thus induced there nucleates voids at the interface and make them grow along the fibers, even if the interface have the same strength as the matrix. The composite is highly heterogeneous in microscopic scale, thus the stress wave is also distorted microscopically. This explains why the cracks and voids appear dispersively. For high impact stress, the transmitted tensile wave may also cause the longitudinal cracking.

Figure 4. Spall damage in composite(3C2).

Figure 5. Spall damage in composite(19C).

Figure 6. Spall damage in 1050 aluminum.

Figure 7. Cracking in fibers(19C).

3.3 Nondestructive evaluation of spall damage with acoustic microscope

Figure 8 shows ultrasonic C-scan image(parallel to the plate face) of the target plate at the depth 3.5mm from the impacted face with a 30MHz focused acoustic lens. The white dots correspond to strongly reflected echoes, namely voids or cracks in the composite. It should be noted that the dot size is not equal to the actual sizes of voids or cracks because of the scattering and diffraction of the ultrasonic waves at the boundary of the voids or cracks. Figure 9 is B-scan image(cross section) along the line X-X in Figure 8. The figure shows that the voids and cracks are distributed within a layer of 1.5mm thick, which is markedly different from 1050 aluminum. SEM observation of this cross section has confirmed the spall damage.

Figure 8. C-scan image of composite(3C2).

Figure 9. B-scan image of composite

4. CONCLUDING REMARKS

The initial spall damage of alumina/aluminum composite reinforced with short fibers was investigated by the plate impact tests. The damage was evaluated with SEM observation, and ultrasonic C- and B-scans. It has been confirmed that the short fibers work effectively to strengthen the threshold stress of spallation even if the fibers are aligned parallel to the impacted surface. The damage evaluation with an ultrasonic microscope enable us to detect nondestructively the spall damage, which will be beneficial to investigate cumulative damage due to repeated impact.

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